

complexes excess cupric ion leading to the formation of a mixed cuprous-cupric mercaptide which in the present case is violet. On adding thioglycollic acid the mixed mercaptide breaks and at the end point the violet colour is replaced by a permanent yellow precipitate of cuprous mercaptide. The overall process is represented by the following equation,

Although iodometry is a common procedure for the determination of copper(II), the method is vitiated by the presence of compounds that react with iodine liberated on adding potassium iodide to copper(II) salt solution. The thioglycollic acid method can tolerate a number of such compounds. No indicator is required for titration and the thioglycollic acid solution is to be checked only after each two weeks.

Experimental

Reagents: A 0.05M solution of copper(II) sulphate was prepared by dissolving a right amount of AnalaR sample in distilled water. Its strength was checked by iodometric titration. Less concentrated solutions were made by appropriate dilution.

An aqueous solution of 0.1M thioglycollic acid was prepared by dissolving an approximate volume of 98-99% pure sample. Its strength was determined by oxidising with a known excess of iodine solution followed by titrating the latter with standard thiosulphate³. Alternatively and if the same burette is to be used for filling thioglycollic acid, the following method may be used.

In a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask 10 ml of 0.1 N iodate solution is taken and treated with 0.5g of potassium iodide plus 3ml of 1M sulphuric acid. The liberated iodine is diluted with 25ml of distilled water and titrated with thioglycollic acid being delivered from a 10-ml burette graduated in 0.02 ml. About 1 ml of 0.5% starch is added only when the solution of the flask is yellow and the blue complex is further titrated to colourless end point. The following reaction occurs

Procedure: A measured volume (about 10-30ml) of copper(II) salt solution (containing about 6-50mg of copper) is taken in a 150-ml Erlenmeyer flask. A 0.05M solution of thioglycollic acid is used, when the sample solution contains upto 23mg of copper and a 0.1M titrant for higher amounts. The contents of the flask are swirled regularly during titration. At the end point the deep violet complex first formed changes to a permanent yellow. Near the end-point the titrant is added slowly with vigorous shaking.

Results

Copper(II) salt with sulphate, nitrate, chloride or acetate may be directly titrated with thioglycollic acid. A pH of 4 is best suited for the titration. In the case

of copper(II) acetate the desired pH may be brought down by dropwise addition of dilute hydrochloric acid. Results for the determination of copper(II) are given in Table 1. It follows from the equation for the reaction

TABLE-1. DETERMINATION OF COPPER WITH THIOLYCOLLIC ACID

Taken	Copper (mg)	Found	± Diff. (mg)
6.40		6.39	- 0.01
12.80		12.72	- 0.08
18.55		18.50	- 0.05
25.60		25.52	- 0.08
30.42		30.49	+ 0.07
36.56		36.46	- 0.10
44.61		44.72	+ 0.11
50.80		51.06	+ 0.26

of copper(II) with thioglycollic acid that 1ml of 0.05M thioglycollic acid is equivalent to 1.5885 mg of copper. The proposed method is accurate to 0.3% with a standard deviation of 0.2%. Cinnamic acid, sodium formate, allyl alcohol, glycine, cystine and zinc, bromide, chloride and sulphite ions can be tolerated. Serious interference is caused by iron(III), lead(II), tin(II), silver(I) and mercury(II) ions.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Mercury(II) with Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide

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SEVERAL β-ketoanilides have been recommended for the gravimetric determination of mercury(II)¹⁻³. This report describes the use of cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide as a reagent for the extraction spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II).

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents: Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide was prepared in the laboratory⁴ and pure mercury(II) nitrate (E. Merck) was used. A citrate buffer of pH 6.5 was prepared from 1g of citric acid (G. R., E. Merck) and sodium hydroxide. A Hilger and Watts H700 Uvispek spectrophotometer was used.

Procedure: Add 1ml of the stock citrate buffer to mercury(II) solution containing 50-450 μg of the metal, dilute to 10 ml, heat to 50° and add 50-60 mg of cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide dissolved in 3-4 ml of ethanol. Adjust the pH to 6.2-8.0 with 2*N* sodium hydroxide solution, cool and extract the complex with two 5 ml portions of isobutyl methyl ketone. Dehydrate the combined extract with sodium sulphate and measure the absorbance at 345 nm against pure solvent within three days.

Results and Discussion

The wave-length of maximum absorbance for the mercury(II) complex was 345 nm where the reagent showed no absorption and Beer's law was valid upto 45 μg of mercury per ml of the solvent.

Fig. 1. Absorbance Curves of Hg(II)-Cyclopentanone-2-Carboxyanilide in isobutylmethyl Ketone.

The complex was extracted in chloroform, benzene and carbon tetrachloride with difficulty. Isobutylmethyl ketone was selected as the extracting solvent due to ease in extraction and the stability of the complex. Approximately 96% of the complex was recovered by one extraction. About 50-60 mg of the reagent was sufficient provided the complex was allowed to form before extraction. Larger amounts of it were required when the extraction was tried with cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide dissolved in the ketone.

Extraction was quantitative above a pH of 6.2. However, mercury(II) (300 μg) could be determined with a relative standard deviation of $\pm 1\%$ in the presence of 0.0 mg of Cu(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Fe(III) or Al(III) provided the pH was adjusted to 7.0-7.5.

Mole-ratio and slope-ratio methods indicated the formation of a mercury(II) bis-complex, the dissociation constant being 5.97×10^{-13} . The Sandell sensitivity was 4.6×10^{-2} μg of mercury(II) per cm^2 while the molar absorptivity at 345 nm was $4400 \pm 4\%$.

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Molecular Interactions—Studies on the Distribution of Aniline between Water and Binary Mixtures of Organic Solvents*

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THE distribution coefficients of aniline between water and binary mixtures of different weight fractions of carbon tetrachloride with benzene or nitrobenzene have been measured at 30° and 40°. The changes in the thermodynamic parameters of free energy, enthalpy and entropy accompanying the transfer of one mole of aniline from the aqueous layer to the organic layer have been calculated.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present investigation were of Analar quality. The organic liquids were purified by the usual procedures¹. Double-distilled water was employed. The weight percentages of the organic solvents in the binary solvent mixtures were calculated from the known volumes of the two solvents and their density values at 30°.

The method adopted for the determination of the distribution coefficient was the conventional one². The initial concentration of aniline in the aqueous layer was kept at 0.01 *M* in all the experiments. In order to

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